

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers:

Everything is getting more and more expensive they say. Well, J.UCS is getting less expensive, even more: as of January 2007, J.UCS will be free for all, including all back-issues! As a sample of open access policy the paper *Plagiarism-A Survey* as well as the other three papers which appear in this issue are generally accessible.

The fact that we are able to join the open access movement has only been made possible through the support of the Graz University of Technology, the KNOW Center and the University of Applied Sciences (CAMPUS '02), all seated in Graz, Austria.

So, please spread the message! Any paper that is now accepted by J.UCS will have still many more readers than it has had before. Maybe J.UCS is the largest and oldest and soon free refereed journal of the world?

As is usual for general issues of J.UCS, i.e. issues that are not devoted to a particular topic, the four papers in this issue deal with rather diverse topics of computer science and thus do nicely justice to the name of our journal. We hope you enjoy reading them!

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
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